

NUTRITION OF SURGICAL PATIENTS

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Annotation In this article, nutrition is a complex process of taking, digesting, absorbing and assimilating food into the body. In addition, it is reflected how the patients in the department are treated.

Key words: Nutrition, function, metabolic processes, therapeutic nutrition, clinical nutrition, carbohydrates, artificial food, enteral nutrition.

Аннотация В этой статье питание представляет собой сложный процесс приема, переваривания, всасывания и усвоения пищи в организме. Кроме того, отражено, как лечат больных в отделении.

Ключевые слова: питание, функция, обменные процессы, лечебное питание, лечебное питание, углеводы, искусственное питание, энтеральное питание.

Nutrition is the most important physiological need of the body. It is necessary for:

1. building and continuous renewal of cells and tissues;
2. supply of energy necessary to replenish the body's energy costs;
3. the intake of substances from which enzymes, hormones, and other regulators of metabolic processes and vital activity are formed in the body.

The metabolism, function and structure of all cells, tissues and organs depend on the nature of nutrition.

Nutrition is a complex process of intake, digestion, absorption and assimilation of nutrients in the body.

Therapeutic nutrition is a scientifically substantiated system of nutrition organization and differentiated use of certain food products and their combinations for therapeutic or prophylactic purposes, sufficient to supply the body with energy.

Basic principles of clinical nutrition. One of the main principles of therapeutic nutrition, as well as nutrition in general, is a balanced diet (the amount of food that provides a person's daily need for nutrients and energy), i.e. observance of a certain ratio of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and water in the proportions necessary for the human body.

Proteins contained in the diet play a huge role in maintaining the normal functioning of the body. They are a building material for organs and tissues, carry out a catalytic (being a component of all enzymes), as well as a transport function, being, in particular, a carrier of lipids and carbohydrates in the form of lipoproteins and glycoproteins; serve as the starting material for the synthesis of hormones, provide protective reactions of the body, participating in the production of antibodies. With a negative nitrogen balance (an imbalance between protein anabolism and catabolism), tissues with a high rate of protein renewal (intestine, hematopoietic organs) suffer first of all, and the body's resistance weakens.

Fats serve mainly as a source of energy, although they also perform other functions in the body (for example, participation in the absorption of fat-soluble vitamins). Their share in the diet should be 30-35% of the total energy value (average 70-105 g per day). Unfortunately, many people have a consumption level of 40-45%. This increase occurs due to the so-called "hidden fats" - carbohydrates contained, for example, in confectionery products and which are later a source of fat formation. An excess of refractory animal fats can contribute to the development of cardiovascular diseases, so at least 1/3 of the daily intake must be vegetable fats. The diet must necessarily include polyunsaturated fatty acids necessary for the synthesis of many biologically active compounds (prostaglandins, etc.).

Carbohydrates are the most important source of energy, their content in the diet should be on average 400-500 g. Their minimum intake should not be lower than 50-

60 g per day in order to avoid increased oxidation of endogenous lipids (with the accumulation of ketone bodies) and the breakdown of tissue (primarily muscle) proteins. Most of the daily diet of carbohydrates (300-400 g) should be taken in the form of products containing starch, a smaller part (50-100 g) - in the form of mono- and disaccharides (glucose, sucrose). Excess carbohydrate intake enhances lipogenesis and contributes to the development of obesity. Reducing the carbohydrate content in food is an essential part of the treatment of diabetes.

In addition to proteins, fats and carbohydrates, the diet should include drinking water (an average of about 1.5 liters per day), vitamins, and trace elements.

When determining the composition of the diet, it is also necessary to take into account its energy value and its correspondence to the body's energy costs - energy consumption to maintain the body's basal metabolism (energy consumption in conditions of complete rest) and various human physical efforts. At the same time, it is taken into account that 1 g of proteins, fats and carbohydrates of food, taking into account their digestibility, gives the body, respectively, 17.2×10^3 , 38.9×10^3 , 17.2×10^3 J (4.1, 9.3 and 4.1 kcal) of energy.

Diet. The most optimal for a healthy person is, as you know, a four-time diet, in which: breakfast includes 25% of the total diet, second breakfast - 15%, lunch – 35%, dinner – 25%. In some diseases, the diet requires a radical change.

Organization of nutrition and feeding of patients. In the organization of nutrition of patients in the hospital, both medical workers and catering workers take part.

The doctor conducting the examination and treatment of the patient prescribes a certain diet to him, making an appropriate mark in the medical history.

The ward nurse makes portions, which indicate the total number of patients receiving one or another table of therapeutic nutrition.

Based on the summation of the data of all portioners in the catering department, the required number of required dishes is prepared. The general daily management

of the nutrition of patients (usually in large hospitals) is carried out by a dietitian who is responsible for the correct preparation and application of therapeutic diets.

The dietitian, in addition, provides consultative assistance to the doctors of the departments regarding the most optimal choice of a therapeutic nutrition table.

The direct management of the work of the catering unit (quality control of products, their laying, cooking, delivery to departments, etc.) is assigned to the hospital dietitian.

Distribution of ready-made food is carried out only after sampling by the doctor on duty of the hospital. The delivery of cooked food to the departments and its distribution must be carried out as quickly as possible, since the cooling of food and its reheating significantly reduce the quality of dishes. Food is distributed by barmaids, feeding the seriously ill is the responsibility of ward nurses.

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Types of nutrition of surgical patients. Nutrition of surgical patients can be:

Natural:

1. active – patients with a general regimen eat themselves;
2. passive – patients on bed rest are fed by a nurse.

Artificial food. Artificial nutrition is used in cases where the patient cannot eat independently or when nutrition in a natural way due to various reasons (severe, debilitating disease, preoperative preparation and postoperative period) is insufficient.

There are several ways to artificial nutrition:

1. through a probe inserted into the stomach; using a gastrostomy or jejunostomy (surgical opening in the stomach and jejunum),
2. through the parenteral administration of various drugs, bypassing the gastrointestinal tract (from the Greek para – near, entera – intestines).

Since a probe is also often used for artificial nutrition when applying a gastrostomy or jejunostomy, the first two methods are often combined into the concept of probe, or enteral, nutrition.

Enteral nutrition. Enteral nutrition is a type of nutritional therapy in which nutrients in the form of special mixtures are administered orally or through a nasogastric tube, nasoduodenal tube, gastrostomy, jejunostomy, etc., when it is impossible to adequately meet the energy and plastic needs of the body naturally in various diseases.

Enteral nutrition is used with the preserved function of the gastrointestinal tract, allows you to maximize the use and maintain the functional activity of the intestine in a physiological way, and therefore has undeniable advantages in comparison with parenteral nutrition. In a long-term non-functioning intestine, degenerative changes

in the villous epithelium develop, and the risk of bacterial translocation (penetration of microbial bodies from the intestinal lumen into the free abdominal cavity and systemic circulation) increases.

Indications for enteral nutrition:

1. protein-energy deficiency;
2. neoplasms localized in the head, neck, stomach;
3. radiation and chemotherapy for oncological diseases;
4. acute and chronic radiation injuries, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract: Crohn's disease, malabsorption syndrome, short loop syndrome, chronic pancreatitis, ulcerative colitis, diseases of the liver and biliary tract;
5. nutrition in pre-and postoperative periods;
6. injury, burns, acute poisoning;
7. complications of the postoperative period (fistulas of the housing and communal services, sepsis, failure of the sutures of anatomists);
8. infectious diseases.

Advantages of enteral nutrition compared to parenteral nutrition:

1. using and maintaining bowel functions,
2. physiology,
3. use of the natural immunological barrier of the intestinal mucosa,
4. the possibility of various methods of administration (oral, nasogastric and nasoenteric tube, gastrostomy, jejunostomy),
5. can be used as a supplement to regular food,
6. cheaper and safer.

As probes for artificial nutrition, soft plastic, rubber or silicone tubes with a diameter of 3-5 mm are used, as well as special probes with olives at the end, which facilitate subsequent control over the position of the probe.

For enteral (tube) nutrition, you can use various mixtures containing broth, milk, butter, raw eggs, juices, homogenized canned meat and vegetable diets, as well as baby food mixtures. In addition, at present, special preparations are produced for

enteral nutrition (protein, fat, oat, rice and other enpits), in which proteins, fats, carbohydrates, mineral salts and vitamins are selected in strictly defined ratios.

The introduction of nutrients through a probe or gastrostomy can be done fractionally, i.e. in separate portions, for example 5-6 times a day; drip slowly, for a long time, as well as with the help of special dispensers that automatically regulate the flow of food mixtures.

Feeding the patient through a tube. In resuscitation and intensive care units for feeding unconscious patients, either permanent gastric tubes are used, which are changed after 1-2 days, or they are introduced for each feeding.

More often, the introduction of a probe with a diameter of 5 mm through the nose is used, a probe with a diameter of 8 mm is inserted only through the mouth for each feeding. To carry out the procedure, it is necessary to prepare: a gastric tube, a Janet syringe, an aerosol can with 10% lidocaine, liquid paraffin, a phonendoscope, a tray, cotton wool, a diaper and liquid food. The nasal passages are cleaned with cotton wool, for the purpose of anesthesia, lidocaine is injected twice, lubricated with vaseline oil. Carefully, with rotational movements, a probe lubricated with vaseline oil is inserted through the nasal passage into the esophagus, and then into the stomach. You need to make sure that the tube is in the stomach. To do this, air is supplied through the probe with the help of a syringe to Zhane and at this time the stomach is auscultated with a phonendoscope installed in the epigastric region – the noise of the blown air is detected (if it enters the trachea, a cough begins).

The introduction of the nutrient mixture is carried out fractionally – 50 ml in 2 minutes, in a volume of 500-800 ml. It is advisable to continuously introduce a nutrient solution, especially in cases where the probe is installed in the small intestine.

When feeding through a gastric tube, it is possible to carry out a fractional administration of a mixture of 200-300 ml every 3-4 hours. With the rapid introduction, especially concentrated mixtures, patients may complain of the occurrence of cramping abdominal pain, diarrhea.

The probe must be washed after each feeding of the patient or, with continuous administration, every 8 hours.

References:

1. Pediatric cardiology for pediatricians. Textbook for universities – Andrey Prakhov.
2. Neonatal cardiology – Andrey V. Prakhov.
3. Pediatric cardiology and rheumatology: A practical guide – Belyaeva L.M.
4. Micha R, Mannar V, Afshin A, Allemandi L, Baker P, Battersby J, et al. 2020 Global nutrition report: action on equity to end malnutrition. 2020.
5. World Health Organization. Essential nutrition actions: mainstreaming nutrition through the life-course. 2019
6. Tashpulatova, D., & Siddiqova, I. (2021, April). A CRITIQUE OF THE VIEW OF ANTONYMY AS A RELATION BETWEEN WORD FORMS. In *Конференции*.
7. qizi Turaboyeva, S. Z., & qizi Tashpulatova, D. X. (2022). O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDAGI AXLOQIY QADRIYATLAR MAZMUNINI IFODALOVCHI BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(1), 143-147.
8. Тошпулатова, Д. Х. (2019). ПОНЯТИЕ И ВИДЫ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ. *Вопросы педагогики*, (7-2), 118-121.
9. ТАШПУЛАТОВА, Д. PRAGMATIC APHORISMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FEATURE AND THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR TRANSMISSION IN THE CORPUS. *СООТНОШЕНИЕ ПАРАЛИНГВИСТИКИ И РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В РАЗНЫХ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРАХ*.
10. Ташпулатова, Д. Х. К., & Умурзакова, Б. Э. (2023). ПЕРВОНАЧАЛЬНАЯ СИСТЕМА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(ТМА Conference), 303-309.

11. Tashpulatova, D. K. K., & Jiyenbayeva, B. (2023). THE IMPACT OF LEARNING A LANGUAGE ON THE BRAIN FUNCTION. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(TMA Conference), 310-314.
12. NAVOI, A., & BABUR, Z. M. (2022). RESEARCH AND EDUCATION